

THE ACQUISITION OF THE ENGLISH VOICES UNDER THE AFFECT OF SOME FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

According to the results of the research on second language acquisition, many factors, including internal ones such as age, personal characteristics, motivation, experience, cognition and mother tongue as well as external ones such as curricula, teaching methods, encouragement, culture, learners' status and approach to native language, affect second language acquisition. In this research, we are interested in the affects of gender, age and register on the second language acquisition of students in learning the English tenses. This independent experimental research reveals that certain results are the same as the previous ones; however, some results are different from the statements of other research.

Key words: Age, gender, register, second language acquisition

1 INTRODUCTION

The second language acquisition is an old issue, but acquiring the passive voice is a new one. Linguistic responses were investigated in particular through the passive acquisition in graders 8 and students major in English. These linguistic responses will be very useful reference materials in linguistics, in general, and in small fields of linguistics, in particular, such as sociolinguistics, psychological linguistics, etc.

The second language acquisition is the central focus of this article. We conduct parallel research at two levels of learning: the acquisition of the passive voice in graders 8 (beginning to learn the passive sentences) and the acquisition of the passive voice in the second-year students major in English.

In terms of teaching methodology, for graders 8, we conducted a survey methodology for analyzing students' errors through learning passive sentences and suggested corrective steps through encouragement and motivation. This method helps students learn passive sentences effectively. For sophomore English students, we conducted concept telling (traditional grammar) and concept checking methods introduced by British Council specialists around the world. Through learning and acquiring passive sentences, both the eighth-graders and the students in the experimental class had linguistic responses. However, these reactions share common points and differences due to the factors of age, gender, and register.

2 RATIONALE

2.1 Gender affects the acquisition of language

According to Anthony, C. Oha, the male and female use different language patterns. Compared to the male, the female are more talkative, more polite, unresponsive, often complaining, nagging, asking more, supporting each other and cooperating easily.

According to the study by Csizer and Dorneyi (2005) [2], in the experimental classes, male students are less motivated, while female students are more positive and active in their studies. The research uses both quantitative and qualitative methods to examine and identify gender differences in the various factors that influence motivation in learning a foreign language. Compared to girls, male students need more encouragement from teachers to be able to learn equally well.

Masoud Zoghi, Seyyed Ali Kazemi and Ali Kalani [11] argue that gender is an important theoretical and pedagogical issue in learning a second language. Gender is considered a variable in the use of foreign language learning methods. In the research female students are superior to male students in learning foreign languages. With specific data, the authors showed that the results of learning foreign languages of the girls is better than the boys'. Maccoby [10], a professor at Stanford University in the United States, in "Gender Differences in Psychology" argues that boys and girls have obvious gender differences in that schoolgirls are of better language ability. His research suggests that there should be solutions to balance differences in language teaching in the classrooms.

Piasecka (2005) [15] suggests that there are gender differences: in many areas the male is better than the female, but in many ones the female is better than the male. In terms of language ability, girls often start speaking earlier than boys and use longer sentences. Girls' pronunciation and grammar are more accurate. So girls have more vocabulary than boys. Moreover, girls are better at spelling, reading and writing.

Through the research by Narendra Rathod (2012) [13], female students are better foreign language learners. They are more sensitive to new linguistic forms and more willing to adopt them. Girls have a more positive attitude towards learning foreign languages and are more motivated.

2.2 Age affects the acquisition of language

Age significantly impacts on learner language acquisition. The reality is that both children and adults are in different needs of learning a foreign language. Adults naturally find that they need more complex languages and need to interpret ideas that are more meaningful. In other words, children lack the pressure and maturity in learning foreign languages.

Most people think that young learners are of certain advantages over older ones. Young learners learn a second language easily and quickly, compared to older learners (Ellis, 2008; Larsen-Freeman, 2008; Mayberry & Lock, 2003). The relationship between age and success in the acquisition of language, although complex in nature, is associated with the critical period

hypothesis. The decisive determinant, or "sensitive period" is defined as "the period when a child acquires the language quickly, easily, and completely without guidance" (Richards & Schmidt, 2002, p.145 [16]). The decisive period hypothesis is that there is a time between birth and time when a child enters adolescence, when language learning becomes quicker and easier than other periods, ie. after puberty. (Larsen-Freeman & Long, 2008) [8].

Yamanda et al. (Cited in Singleton, 1989) [17] studied 30 primary students aged 7 to 10. These students had not studied English before. In the study, they used 40 words to teach and recorded the results. The results show that older students are weaker than their younger counterparts.

Mark Patkowski (1982) [14] also examined the English proficiency of 67 immigrants in the United States. His work shows that pre-teens acquire language better than students after puberty. He also outlined two other factors - the length of time and the volume of instruction - associated with the age factor.

In contrast, according to a study by Snow and Hoefnagel-Hohle (1982) [18] in the Netherlands, older people learn faster than children and have higher rates of language learning. Based on the analysis of age factors on the basis of critical time hypotheses and related variables, David Singleton (2003) [17] also suggested that in the long run, young students' tendency to acquire better vocabulary when learning a foreign language is not right. According to the report by Lightbown and Spada (2008) [9], learning depends on the characteristics of the learner and the environments. The results show that older learners are more capable of problem solving and more metaphorical abilities than younger learners.

Ekstrand (1982) [4] studied and concluded that the age factor has a strong impact on learner acquisition levels through the quality and volume of foreign language teaching. According to him, the more brain develops, the more appropriate it is to learn a foreign language.

Stephens Krashen (1979) [19] made three suggestions in the field of syntax and morphology:

- Adults learn syntax and morphology faster than children in early stage (when time and approach are the same).
- Older children acquire faster than younger children (when time and approach are the same).
- Students who acquire natural language during adolescence are likely to be more proficient than adults (Singleton, 1989, p. 117). [17]

Anan Fathman (1982) [5] studied the differences in learning phonology, morphology and syntax of English based on age differences. She studied and found that children aged 11 to 15 learn phonology, morphology and syntax in English better than children aged 6 to 10.

According to Mayberry (2003) [12], young learners may not have the motive of the external environment and have no specific goals in learning another language. It is also noted that children and adults do not always have the same qualities and quantities of language input in both formal and informal contexts of learning (Lightbown & Spada, 2008).

2.3 Register affects the acquisition of language

According to Anthony C. Oha (2008) [1], the location of students' living, studying and working will affect their language learning. First, the local language (dialect) will affect learners' language learning. Learners' Latin language will help them get used to the style of writing in English, whether they use French, German or Italian, etc. The pronunciation of different registers will cause Asian learners to speak English not as well as European ones. Moreover, remote locations cause disadvantages for learners to learn foreign languages such as lack of facilities, even lack of teachers and language learning is patchy. While teaching, teachers must pay attention to these factors to help level up the language acquisition gap among the learners.

When studying the English acquisition of students from many countries around the world in a US classroom, Mark S. Patkowski (1982) [14] found a little difference in the academic performance of students, although they are of the same age or gender. The geographic influence of different countries has made the English language acquisition of students uneven.

Surveying an English class in Tokyo, Yamanda and his colleagues noted students from different regions other than those born and raised in Tokyo. Their English acquisition is of slight difference. He and his team said that the geographic location of the students' past lives has influenced the learning of foreign languages, although this influence is very small.

3 FACTORS INFLUENCE STUDENTS' ACQUISITION IN THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Gender

Through the survey of 10 eighth graders, including 6 girls and 4 boys, we found the effects of gender on students' language.

The effects on the English morphology

Through 10 students' assignments and by calling students to the board, we found that the error rate of morphology of male students was higher than that of female students.

The errors of inflectional suffixes:

Ex: English is speaked in the classroom. (Wrong)

English is spoken in the classroom. (Right)

When changing to past participle, students should not use the suffix ED as this is an irregular verb.

The errors of derivational suffixes:

Ex: The writor is sent a letter. (Wrong)

The writer is sent a letter. (Right)

The "write" verb takes suffix ER, not OR when it is converted to "writer".

Morphological errors		
	Derivational suffix	Inflectional suffix
Boys	50%	75%
Girls	16,6%	33,3%

The effects on the English syntax

In the study on syntax errors, male students also make more errors than female ones.

Ex: The books is put on the table. (Wrong)

The books are put on the table. (Right)

In the active sentence "He puts the books on the table", the verb "puts" is conjugated in the singular form in accordance with the subject "He", but in the passive sentence, the subject "the books" is in the plural form. Thus, the verb "to be" conjugated according to the new subject is "are", not "is".

Syntactic errors	
Boys	75%
Girls	33,3%

General comment on the effect of gender on language

In terms of morphology, the boys made 50% errors of derivational suffixes and 75% ones of inflectional suffixes, while the girls made 16.6% and 33, 3% respectively.

In terms of syntax, the boys errors made up 75%, while the girls made up 33.3%.

According to Susan M. Gass and Larry Selinker, male teenagers are more mature and cautious than female ones. Although their levels are the same, the girls are more elaborate and accurate. Therefore, the female students are less likely to commit morphological and syntactic errors.

3.2 Age

Most 8th graders (80%) are 14 years old, only two (20%) are 15 years old. We classify them into two groups for the survey.

Through the survey, although the difference in learning outcomes was very blurred between the two groups, we still have the following remarks:

Morphological errors

The 14-year-old group committed more morphological errors than the 15-year-old one. We believe that better life experience helped older students recognize morphological errors and avoid them. On the contrary, younger students with less experience are less likely to commit these errors.

Morphological error rate by age

Groups of students	Morphological errors	Rate
14-year-old group	5	85%
15-year-old group	1	15%

Syntactic errors

The group of eight 14-year-olds made four syntactic errors and the group of two fifteen-year-olds made one error. Both groups made the same syntactic errors. The error rate is the same between the number of errors and students.

Syntactic error rate by age

Groups of students	Syntactic errors	Rate
14-year-old group	4	80%
15-year-old group	1	20%

3.3 Register

In the group of ten 8th graders, all of them were born and raised in Ho Chi Minh City. However, there are two ethnic Chinese students in this 8th grader group. During their study, these two students learned better than the rest of the students. In terms of pronunciation, the students are equally capable. But in terms of agility, Chinese students show quicker reflexes and learn lessons better.

The following table shows that Chinese students get a higher average mean score than Kinh students:

	Kinh group	Chinese group
Marks	5, 6, 6, 6, 7, 7, 7, 8	7, 8
Mean	6.5	7.5

The average score of Chinese students, 7.5, is higher than the average score of Kinh students, 6.5. Due to the use of two languages when communicating, Chinese students are more experienced than Kinh students, who use only one language when communicating. This language advantage made it easier for Chinese students to acquire the passive voice better.

4 THE FACTORS AFFECTING THE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' ACQUISITION THROUGH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS:

4.1 Age

We conducted experiments in twenty-four students aged 17-24 and eight students aged over twenty-four years old. We call these two groups young and old. The group of young students actively participated in group activities and they attended the class more often. The older group, on the other hand, were slower and more timid when they participated in group activities; moreover, they were not usually present in class.

4.2 Gender

The female students in the experimental class outnumber men. During the class, the female students participated in activities more actively. They specifically discussed concept questions more enthusiastically, and contributed more ideas to the answers. Moreover, the female students were rarely absent from the class while the male students were often absent for many reasons. After the course, the female students felt more satisfied and they wanted to study more.

4.3 Register

The students at Saigon University come from different regions throughout the country. The students from big cities will take more advantages when they learn passive sentences, while students from remote areas take more disadvantages such as ones in pronunciation, grammar, and ability to listen and speak English fluently.

Psychologically, in the experimental class we found that the group of young students was more active and dynamic than the old ones. Therefore, the young students were more motivated when they knew how to convert sentences with concept checking.

4.4 The effects of gender on students' language

Based on a survey of experimental students including 27 females and 5 males, we found significant effects of gender on students' language.

The effects on English morphology

Despite university students, who had studied English for seven years in high school, the students still made morphological errors. Through our surveys on 32 student papers, we found that the error rate of the male students was higher than that of the female students.

The errors of inflectional suffixes:

Ex: A mother birth feeds babies in the nest. (Active)

Babies are feeded by a mother bird in the nest. (Passive: morphological error of the verb)

Babies are fed by a mother bird in the nest. (Right)

Changing the verb to past participle, the students should not use suffix ED for "feed" because it is an irregular verb.

The errors of derivational suffixes:

Ex: The trainers were taught in a workshop. (Wrong)

The trainees were taught in a workshop. (Right)

The noun "trainer" has an ER suffix meaning "doer". The noun "trainee" has the EE suffix meaning "attendee, learner". The students think the verb "train" will have the ER suffix like "learner", "player", "reader", and so on.

Morphological errors		
	Derivational suffix	Inflectional suffix
Male students	27%	36%
Female students	9,6%	19,2%

The effects on English syntax

Just like junior high school students, in the survey on syntactic errors, the male students also made more errors than the female students.

Ex: Ms. Smith took care of the children. (Active)

The children was taken care of by Ms. Smith. (Wrong)

The children were taken care of by Ms. Smith. (Right)

In the passive sentence "The children was taken care of by Ms. Smith", the verb "was" conjugated in singular form does not match the subject "The children". The verb "to be" should be conjugated "were" to match the subject "the children" in plural form. Therefore, "The children were taken care of by Smith" is the correct sentence.

Syntactic errors	
Male students	18%
Female students	9,6%

General comment on the effect of gender on language

In terms of morphology the percentage of the male students who made errors of derivational suffixes was 27% and the one of inflectional suffixes was 36%, while the rate of girls who made errors of derivational suffixes was 9.6% and the one of inflectional suffixes was 19.2%.

In terms of syntax the male students who made errors make up 18%, while female students make up 9.6%.

According to Susan M. Gass and Larry Selinker, at teenage female students are more mature and more careful than male students. Although the levels of the students are the same, but the male

students do their papers hastily and inaccurately. Therefore, male students commit more morphological and syntactic errors.

4.5 The effect of age on students' language

The second-year students at Saigon University are of relatively equal age, little different. According to statistics, we divided the students into two groups: group 1 comprised 83.6% of students aged 17-24 and the remaining group comprised 16.3% of students aged over 24.

When examining the errors of these two groups of students, we found that the students made the following errors:

Rate of students' morphological errors:

The group 1 students (17 to 24 years old) are less likely to make morphological errors. The rate was 7.2% of inflectional suffixes and 3.6% of derivational suffixes.

The group 2 students (over the age of 24) made more morphological errors. The error rate is 40% of inflectional suffixes and 20% of derivational suffixes.

Morphological errors		
	Derivational suffixes	Inflectional suffixes
Group 1 students	3,6%	7,2%
Group 2 students	20%	40%

Rate of students' syntactic errors:

On subject and verb concord, the group 1 students made up 3.6% and the group 2 students made up 20%.

The following table illustrates the syntactic errors of the students in two groups:

Syntactic errors	
Group 1 students	3,6%
Group 2 students	20%

General comment on the effect of age on language

In terms of morphological errors, the percentage of students in the first group who made derivational errors was 3.6% and the one of inflectional errors was 7.2%, while the percentage of students in the second group who made derivational errors was 20% and the one of inflectional errors was 40%.

In terms of syntactic errors, the percentage of students in group 1 making errors was 3.6%, while the percentage of students in group 2 making errors was 20%.

According to Stephens Krashen [19], the acquisition of young learners is better than that of older

ones. Although the age difference is small, language acquisition is different. The more different age is, the more different acquisition is. It is much better for young people and more difficult for old ones to learn a foreign language.

4.6 The effect of register on students' language

In the experimental class of Saigon University, students come from different provinces and regions. We conducted a survey of differences across tests because of the assumption that Vietnam's geographic and dialectical elements also partially affected the acquisition of English passive sentences.

Within a small class of 32 students, we divided the class into two groups: one student group living in Ho Chi Minh City and the other group of students from other provinces and regions.

The effects on English morphology

The students in the group from provinces and regions throughout the country committed more morphological errors than students in the Ho Chi Minh City group. Through a survey of 32 student assignments, we found that the morphological error rate was as follows:

Errors of inflectional suffixes:

Ex: The company has used a lot of means to control the business. (Active)

A lot of means has been used to control the business by the company. (Errors of subject and verb concord)

"Means" is an irregular noun with a zero inflectional suffix (unchanged) in plural form. Based on the morphological environment of "a lot of", this is a plural noun, so the verb must be conjugated accordingly:

A lot of means have been used to control the business by the company.

Errors of derivational suffixes:

The word "trainers" in the example "The trainers were taught in a workshop" is also a part of the passive sentence translation exercises that the students from provinces did wrongly. Particularly, the students in Ho Chi Minh City did correctly in the case.

Morphological errors		
	Derivational suffixes	Inflectional suffixes
Students from HCM	0%	10%
Students from other places	19,8%	33%

The effects on English syntax

The students in the provinces made more syntactic errors than the ones in Ho Chi Minh City.

Ex: This factory makes a wide range of products. (Active)

A wide range of products is made by this factory. (Wrong)

A wide range of products are made by this factory. (Right)

"A wide range of products" is considered plural, so the verb in plural form will be appropriate. The "A wide range" element at the beginning of the noun phrase made students think that this was a singular noun phrase.

Syntactic errors	
Students from HCM	20%
Students from other places	50%

General comment on the effect of register on language

The percentage of the students in the provinces with morphological and syntactic errors is always higher than the one of the students living in Ho Chi Minh City. This is a proven practice in language learning to date on the high school graduation examinations. Due to difficult circumstances and poor learning conditions, the students in provinces, in general, are negatively affected when learning foreign languages, especially English.

5 CONCLUSION

The acquisition of the passive sentences of high school and university students is affected by many factors, especially age, gender and register. Due to their low basic background, the students can only acquire simple sentences. Particularly, the high school students of older age in the group absorbed better, but in the experimental class, the university students of higher age acquired less. On gender, in both classes of high school and university students, the female are always better absorbed. In terms of register, the high school and university students in the big cities are better than the ones in remote areas.

Gender, age and register factors significantly affect the acquisition of the high school and university students. These effects make some difference in foreign language acquisition. In order to create fairness in gender and to bridge the gap in foreign language learning outcomes of the regions, the Government and the Ministry of Education and Training should set the policies to support the students in the remote areas to learn better and invest in the gender research. The interesting thing here is to help the high school and university male students learn languages as well as the female ones.

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